

Restoring the cab of CPR 2858

Canadian Pacific's "Royal Hudsons"

- "Hudson" refers to a 4-6-4 wheel arrangement
 - A preferred type of the CPR
 - 65 locomotives in 5 subclasses (H1a through H1e)
- 1939 Royal Tour of Canada
 - CPR responsible for the westbound Royal Train
 - Train hauled by nearly new H1d #2850 in special livery
 - 3,224 miles (5,189 km) without failure or replacement
- CPR given permission to use the term "Royal"
 - Applied only to semi-streamlined engines
 - H1c (2830-2849), H1d (2850-2859), H1e (2860-2864)
 - Engines carried crowns on running boards

CPR 2858

- H1d, built by Montreal Locomotive Works in August 1938
- Worked out of Montreal for most of its active life
 - Ran through to Chapleau on transcontinental trains
 - Over 100,000 (160,000 km) miles annually
- Last overhaul October 1956
 - Subsequently stored serviceable for extended periods
 - No record of use after December 1959
- Arrived Angus Shops for the last time July 26, 1960
 - Remark on report: “Hold for possible sale”
 - 2,297,192 miles (3,675,507 km) in total

In The Scrap Line

- Spent six years in the Angus scrap line
 - Photo was taken October 22, 1962
 - Ultimately one of the last two survivors
- Acquired by National Museum of Science and Technology in 1966
 - CP's last two other steam engines also purchased
 - G5a 4-6-2 #1201 (the other Angus survivor)
 - K1a 4-8-4 #3100 (from Weston Shops)

On to Ottawa

- Before leaving Angus Shops the locomotive got a cosmetic restoration
 - it was “restored to pristine appearance” [1]
 - “The paint shop outdid itself to produce a splendid job” [2]
 - “The grey iron foundry foreman himself cast the replacements for the long missing crowns” [2]
- Moved to CPR’s Ottawa West facility on April 13, 1967
 - The other engine visible in the photo is 1201
 - Note connecting rods on running boards

[1] Omar Lavallee

[2] Trains Magazine, August 1969

In the Museum

- Installed in museum's "Locomotive Hall" beside 3100
- Bridge placed between the two cabs
- Stairways provided to cab doors
- No barriers inside cabs
- Public free to "touch and feel"

The Consequences

- Vision was very ill-rewarded
- Cabs were thoroughly vandalized
- Not just initials on the paint, etc.
- Fittings, gauges, pipes and so on systematically removed.
- The photo shows the fireman's side of 3100's cab as it is today

Rock Bottom

- In 2002 all asbestos was taken out of the two cabs
- Boiler jackets and other items were removed in doing this
- On 2858 these items were not replaced afterwards
- Cab left thoroughly stripped

The Project

- Longtime Bytown Railway Society (BRS) member and guiding spirit Duncan duFresne died on June 12th, 2012
- BRS suggested that restoring 2858's cab would be a fitting memorial
 - Duncan was a CPR fireman in his earlier years
 - He thoroughly approved of the Hudsons and actually worked on 2858
 - The condition of its cab was a sore point with him
- The museum agreed to the proposal and the project was launched
- BRS is both covering the cost of the restoration and providing the labour
- An ex-museum employee acts as the museum's ears and eyes
 - Now working for the museum on a term contract
 - BRS pays for the portion of his time spent on 2858
- BRS also liaises directly with museum management

Project Goal

The goal is to visually restore the cab to the condition that it would ideally have been in near the end of locomotive's working life.

- All systems to be complete and properly plumbed
 - No pipes ending in space
 - Components functional where feasible (some dummies acceptable)
 - Cab should serve as an illustration of the technology
- Appearance to be as impressive as possible
 - Damaged, worn, and poorly made parts to be replaced where practical
 - e.g. corroded boiler jacket panels
 - Valves to be left in bare metal rather than painted, etc.
 - Not “as it probably was” (dirty, etc.) but more “show cab”
- Educational issues to be taken into account
 - Spare sight glasses relocated to a visible position
 - All valves to be labelled
- Protective barrier to be installed (by museum)

Resources

- The museum's extensive collection of CPR drawings
 - Good for component details
 - Of little help with piping arrangements
- Cab photographs (sadly rare)
 - One excellent "as built" shot of an H1c cab (Mattingly collection)
 - One poor "as built" shot of an H1d cab (a number of publications)
 - Three snaps of 2858's cab as it was in 1967
- 2850
 - Preserved at Exporail (Montreal)
- 1993 museum condition report
 - Compiled with Duncan's assistance
- Service records
 - The museum has these for 1946 onwards
 - Very terse and only give clues as to modifications made
- Experimentation
 - Compressed air useful in tracing under jacket piping
- Modification directives??
 - Do these exist somewhere??

Drawings

- This is a small portion of the large H1d backhead piping drawing
- Very light on piping details
 - Intent was just to give the builder the general idea
- Locomotives may not have matched drawings even when new
 - e.g. Sprinkler valve location
- Many changes made during service lives
 - e.g. Sand disturber removed, separate steam heat gauge
- Some things not shown at all
 - e.g. Valves for window defoggers, cylinder cocks

Photographs (I)

This is one of three shots (from Kevin Day) showing the cab as it was in 1967

- Cab not in ideal condition even before vandalism
 - No Cut-Off Control gauge, brake telltale disconnected, jacket eroded
 - Parts removed at Ottawa West?
- Many parts visible are now missing
- Standard air gauge plumbing??

Photographs (II)

From “Canadian Transportation” (same shot has also appeared elsewhere)

- “As built” cab shot of a booster equipped H1d (probably 2853)
 - Resolution unfortunately very poor
- Tray above firedoor, try cocks above engineer’s gauges
 - Later no tray, cocks on water column
- No separate steam heat gauge
 - Later separate gauge on “ear” added to fireman’s gauge plate
- Sprinkler valve not where shown on drawings

2850

- Booster equipped
- Incomplete
 - Pipes stolen
 - Components missing
- Very dissimilar to 2858
 - Wood lined cab
 - Blowdown on fireman's side
 - Elesco "Steam Dryer"
 - Individual stoker gauges
 - Proper air and water manifolds
 - Six element rocking grate
 - Casing around stoker manifold
 - And so on...
- CPR shops appear to have had a lot of freedom to improvise

Service Reports

CANADIAN PACIFIC RAILWAY COMPANY
MECHANICAL DEPARTMENT

M.P. 11

Port of Shop Repairs Made Montreal Shop Angas Date Nov. 12, 1956
 Engine Number 2858 Date out of Service Sept. 6, 1956 Machinery No. 1
 Class E-1-D Date put into Shop Sept. 19, 1956 Tubes No. _____
 District Quebec Date turned out Oct. 22, 1956 Fire Box No. _____
 Station _____

PARTS OF ENGINE		REPAIRS MADE
#145 Air Compressors	All cyls. OK, new M.V. bush, new rev. rod & piston, all new rings & valves	
Air Reservoirs and Piping	Repaired, automatic drain valves, all cyls. OK, 1 new & 1 used rev. rod, Angas made steam rings.	
Water Pump & Piping # 382		
Ash Pan and Doors	Repaired & tested, Rear: Repaired & tested	
Bell and Ringer	Repaired/Overhauled & repaired/Repaired	
XXXXX Brake- Hds, R.S. & W. Vis. rods/rods/rods, & Cts. gears repd. & tested, str. nuts, fls.		
Brake, Driving and Equipment	Repaired, cross equal, 10 up. H.C. pins, rollers repd. & rebushed	
Brake, Engine Truck	Repaired, 6 hrs. H.C. pins, rollers repd. & rebushed, cross equal, center,	
Brake, Tender Truck	Repaired, 6 hrs. H.C. pins, rollers repd. & rebushed, cross equal, center,	
Buffer Beam Front, and Coupler	Repaired/	

“#382” - a modification order number ?

“Automatic drain valves”

- Service reports confirmed the function of a feed water pump accessory
- Otherwise interesting but of limited use
- Modification orders would be much more useful if they could be found

An Object Lesson

- The remains of the pressure gauge on 3100 are not original.
- The original gauge was “liberated” while the engine was in the scrap line at Weston and has since been donated to the 2858 project.
- The gauge (now vandalized) that came with 2858 is perhaps also a replacement
 - Should be 0-500 psi but is only 0-400 psi
- What can be trusted?

Very Strange Indeed

The pipe leading to 2858's air operated cylinder cocks has a pipe plug put in it and the cylinder cock operating valve is missing. Are we to assume that

- The locomotive ended its operating life with non-functional cylinder cocks?
- The operating valve was stolen while the locomotive was at the museum and those responsible were sufficiently considerate to install the plug?
- The operating valve was taken for other purposes while the engine was in the scrap line and the CPR employee who did this put a plug in through force of habit?
- The disconnected pipe was noticed during the locomotive's cosmetic restoration and a plug was put in to make the missing parts a bit less obvious?

The brake stand is another example of this sort of thing. As found, all pipes leading to it were disconnected, and all of the ports in the base were plugged.

Progress (I)

- Condition of cab framework (ceiling, walls, etc.) greatly improved
 - Most of floor completely redone
 - Corroded panels replaced, rotten wood renewed, etc. etc.
 - Still imperfect but doing better would require a complete rebuild

Progress (II)

- Seats and armrests completely reconditioned
 - New upholstery
- Boiler jacket renewed
 - Complex corner pieces repaired and reused
 - Rest is almost entirely new material
- Complete set of gauges produced (by Alan Westland)
 - Some make use of surviving cases and other parts
 - Others manufactured entirely from scratch
- Plumbing essentially all worked out
 - We have a very good idea of how it all worked and what should go where
 - Only a few little details remain unresolved
 - Function of signal system pipe in front of engineer
 - Cab portion of automatic drains for feed water pump

Progress (III)

- Replacements found for most missing valve parts
 - Some replica parts manufactured
 - Some parts found in museum stores
 - Some parts borrowed from 3100
- Miscellaneous other work
 - Throttle handle overhauled
 - Foam meter transformed from a bare shell to a thing of beauty
 - New locks made for shaker bars
 - New brake stand shroud fabricated
 - Etc, etc.
- Reinstallation of components has begun

Though much work remains to be done the cab is beginning to look presentable as this is written, and by the time of the conference it should look better yet.

Questions???

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